

CHALLENGES BEFORE INDIAN DEMOCRACY

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Abstract

India is called the largest democracy in the world. It is Democratic because election take place at the regular intervals at different at levels. It is almost over 7 decades that elected governments of People's Representative have strengthened our democracy at the Centre, state and local levels. In speed of all these achievements, several formidable challenges remain: exploding population, wide spread average illiteracy, corruptions, economic inequality, political violence, nexalism, communalism and terrorism etc. this research paper is discussed about concept of democracy development of Indian democracy. There is a lot of issue and challenges faced by the Indian democracy for a better understanding of the same; we discuss this in this research paper.

Keywords:- *Democracy, challenges, regionalism, casteism, corruption, nexalism, terrorism, politics, and violence.*

Introduction:-

The world's largest democratic nation is India. Being the world's largest democracy makes us proud. For over 75 years, we have seen successful elections, nonviolent political transitions, state and federal governance, and the exercise of people's rights to free speech, movement, and religion. India has also experienced economic and social development and transformation. At the same time we quite often, listen complaints about prevalent inequalities, in justice or non-fulfillment of Expectations of certain sections of the society (Vora, Palshikar-2004).

They do not consider themselves to be part of the democratic process. Government of the people is the primary goal of democracy; for and by the people, this means that democracy encompasses not just the electoral process but also the entire sense of the people's social and economic aspirations. In India, we continue to discuss the many facets of

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democracy, including its successes, problems, and difficulties. Important issue like horse trading in politics, the anti-defections law pros and cons of a post-poll alliances, and discretionary power of the governor has proud to light the various challenges facing Indian democracy (Hindustan times-1998).

Objective of paper:-

1. To, understand the concept of democracy.
2. To, understand the development of Indian democracy.
3. To, identify current issue and challenges being faced by the Indian democracy.
4. To, explain the role of citizens in a making and efficient and successful democracy.
5. To, suggest some correct you measures for improving the Indian democracy.

Democracy:-

In India, the government is democratic. In a nutshell, democracy is a form of government where the people themselves have sovereignty and the government is reliant on their agreement. The ability to make decisions that no other higher authority may ever have is known as sovereignty. In a democracy, the people or all of the citizens exercise this supreme power. Former President of the United States of America, Abraham Lincoln said "Democracy is a government of the people for the people and by the people" the term democracy comes from the Greek word democratic which means 'rule of the people' (Lotia RM-1955).

Emerging issue and challenges:-

Since few decades and last decades Indian democracy has first numbers to challenges as well as their lots of issue are created by political parties and leaders. New ethical transgressions there are emerging trends such as the criminalization of politics, political violence, and horse trading in politics. That has an impact on the nation's general populace today, since it appears that Indian democracy is not operating effectively in any form. Since independence, India has operated as a responsible democracy. The world community has acknowledged the same. It has effectively adjusted to the difficult circumstance. There have been free and fair periodic elections for all political offices from the panchayate to the president. There has been smooth transfer of a political power from the political parties or set or political parties to other both of the national and state level on many occasions (The Times of India 2012). India is a very large country full of diversity is culturally linguistically and religiously. At the time of independence it was economically under developed. Their wear enormous relational disparities, wide spread poverty, illiteracy, unemployment and shortening almost all public welfare means. Some challenges were found like illiteracy,

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poverty, gender discrimination, casteism, religious fundamentalism, communalism, corruption and criminalization of politics etc. All are the major challenges in front of Indian democracy.

Anti-defections law does not seem to be doing much to stop MLA's from defecting. This is primarily because MLA offered back door entry to assemblies by rival parties. Ethics of post-poll alliances, unlike pre-poll alliances, where the voters are aware of whom they are voting for, post-poll alliances present a new set of challenges. The post-poll alliance is seen as betrayal of the trust of the voters by many misuse of data on social media to influence important political outcomes.

Role of common peoples in an Indian democracy:-

The ordinary people, or Indian citizens, play a crucial role in democracy. Do we as Indian citizens truly understand the role that citizens play in democracy? Why is this crucial job for a thief? People generally assume that other governments rule over them, and they must respect and obey the political power. They are there to be governed. But don't you think that this is not so in a democracy? The people who are citizen in a democratic system like India cannot and ought not to remain passive and tract them as Governed. In fact a democracy can be successful and vibrant only when citizens in bed and reflect in their mind set thinking and behavior the basic value like equality freedom secularism Social Justice uncountable and respect for all. They have to appreciate the opportunities for their desired role and play pro-active rolls to actualize the goals of democracy (The Hindu -2018).

Political Equality:-

Political equality, of course, is just one of the many new things that equality can gain. This implies that every individual in a democratic nation has equal political rights. For example, one can reach out to the impoverished, whereas the other cannot. Political equality implies that this is contested. The constitution of India both will have one vote same time democracy is called the government run on the will of one man one vote. Ashirvatham define. A democratic society is one in which the spirit of equality and fraternity prevails (Ranade -1971).

Democracy and corruption in India:-

Indian politics has been pleasure by corruption for decades. A wave of the scandal angle with the Congress-leads coalition's government that assumed power is 2010. Various accusations we are made in relation to 2010 Commonwealth games. A special committee is established by the Indian government to look into alliances against the chair of the organizing

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committee for the games and other officials. In yet another significant controversy, Andhi Muthu Raja, the Indian telecom minister, was imprisoned on corruption accusations pertaining to the country's 2G spectrum license agreement. The coalition government's support for the case was ultimately rejected. **Research Methodology:-**

The secondary sources are used in this paper the secondary sources of information the newspaper articles of research journal, Thesis and books of the famous philosophers.

Conclusion:-

The correct you measures that are needed to meet the challenges to Indian democracy are focused around the issue and concern unlike Universal literacy that is education for all, poverty alleviation, elimination of gender discrimination, removal of regional imbalances, administrative and judicial reformer and sustained economic, social and environmental development. Indian democracy can adequately respond to all the challenges when it moves forward on the path of the sustainable development. Sustainable development is the pattern of using resources that AIIMS to meet human needs while preserving the environment so that these needs can be made not only in the present but also for the future generation to come.

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